

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE EDUCATION OF SPECIALIZED BOARDING SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, an idea is put forward about the pedagogical possibilities of educating national and universal qualities in the students of specialized boarding schools established in our republic today. After all, how are the national and universal human qualities, which are initially formed in the family, instilled by the pedagogues in the students of the specialized boarding school, who are educated separately from the family today?*

Keywords: *national and universal human qualities, specialized boarding school students, family, moral culture.*

The education system has a special place in further strengthening of national independence, ensuring the succession of ancestors and generations, training patriotic personnel in line with world requirements, and being among the developed countries. In this regard, in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 19, 2021 No. PQ-5188 "On additional measures to further improve the activities of the President, creativity and specialized schools", in the wide-scale reforms implemented in the field of education in our country, students of specialized boarding schools have national and one of the priority issues is to educate the whole human being virtuous. As the head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoev noted, "Today's education means innovation, new consciousness, new thinking and practical action. Our children, who feel today's sharp changes more than anyone else, should adapt to the demands of the times and never forget their identity and national values. [1] On the other hand, qualities formed on the basis of national and universal values are an important means of organizing a person's conscious life. The socio-political implementation of the idea of national and universal human values, in the "Strategy of Development" designed until 2030 can't. The Uzbek people have gained respect in the world community due to their observance of national traditions, noble customs and rituals.[2]

It is known to us that inculcation of national and universal qualities in the mind first of all starts from the family, and it is passed from person to person, from generation to generation through the family, dynastic ideology, grandfather's education, father's personal example, mother's love, and is imprinted in the mind and consciousness of the child. From this point of view, a healthy family-based society and state will be strong in moral, ideological and educational terms. A well-rounded person grows up in such a family, these qualities are reflected in his feelings, understanding and outlook. Pupils of Presidential schools and specialized boarding schools established in each region by the initiative of the head of our state are studying in the educational institution during the week. Pupils of this educational institution are educated and educated most of the time away from the family circle.

How do our pedagogues bring national and universal qualities to students of specialized boarding schools? What pedagogical methods and tools are used, are they effective? Only when

the pedagogical process is purposefully organized, conditions will be created for the development of national and universal values of students in the educational process. In specialized boarding schools, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the formation of good qualities of students from a young age, the knowledge, spirituality, behavior and behavior of the pedagogue are of great importance in solving life issues. It is possible to form children's virtue of living with a sense of the Motherland, national responsibility by increasing high ideological and educational knowledge in an educational institution. In this sense, responsibility is every action of a person, is the ability to understand what will benefit him and his family, fully imagining the product of his work. A person who feels responsible always carefully plans his work, can foresee its consequences and is able to mobilize all his strength and potential to achieve the necessary result. The most convenient way to achieve this is first of all to increase the ideological knowledge of pedagogues, to form healthy thinking and a new scientific outlook in them. The main goal of scientific work is to organize effective pedagogical forms and methods of raising a spiritually mature generation based on the development of new Uzbekistan, rich cultural and historical heritage, national traditions, national and universal values. A person who feels responsible always carefully plans his work, can foresee its consequences and is able to mobilize all his strength and potential to achieve the necessary result. The most convenient way to achieve this is first of all to increase the ideological knowledge of pedagogues, to form healthy thinking and a new scientific outlook in them. The main goal of scientific work is to organize effective pedagogical forms and methods of raising a spiritually mature generation based on the development of new Uzbekistan, rich cultural and historical heritage, national traditions, national and universal values. A person who feels responsible always carefully plans his work, can foresee its consequences and is able to mobilize all his strength and potential to achieve the necessary result. The most convenient way to achieve this is first of all to increase the ideological knowledge of pedagogues, to form healthy thinking and a new scientific outlook in them. The main goal of scientific work is to organize effective pedagogical forms and methods of raising a spiritually mature generation based on the development of new Uzbekistan, rich cultural and historical heritage, national traditions, national and universal values. is to form healthy thinking and a new scientific outlook in them. The main goal of scientific work is to organize effective pedagogical forms and methods of raising a spiritually mature generation based on the development of new Uzbekistan, rich cultural and historical heritage, national traditions, national and universal values. is to form healthy thinking and a new scientific outlook in them. The main goal of scientific work is to organize effective pedagogical forms and methods of raising a spiritually mature generation based on the development of new Uzbekistan, rich cultural and historical heritage, national traditions, national and universal values.

Also, it is considered as a result of scientific research that students of a specialized boarding school have national qualities on the ground of national values [3]:

- Moral purity, faith, honesty, religion, honor, kindness;
- Hospitality, humanity;
- Justice, equality, harmonious neighborliness;
- Struggle for peace and stability, freedom of conscience;
- Not forgetting relatives;
- Respect for elders, kindness for children;
- Honoring the memory of great ancestors, helping neighbors, neighbors, acquaintances;

- Honoring parents at a high level, honoring them, honoring them, never forgetting their respect, always being the first to say hello, fulfilling filial duties;
- Strict adherence to the rules of etiquette, talking with elders and seniors in a modest and polite manner, not saying inappropriate words to them, not insulting the person, not letting go of the idea;
- Respecting elders, fathers, enlightened mothers in the first place, giving greetings regardless of acquaintances or strangers; skip ahead if they meet on the road; showing favoritism;
- Do not forget Uzbek folk tales, legends, myths and epics, proverbs, proverbs, aruz verses, tunes and songs;
- Formation of pride in national traditions, national culture, honesty, piety and kindness in young people;
- To put the respect of scholars and teachers in their place;
- Courage, humanity, humility, fairness, honesty and understanding of justice;
- Religious values, adherence to their moral rules;
- Conducting marriages, circumcisions and cradles;
- Paying attention to various festivals, harvest festivals, melon festivals, flower festivals, many feasts, bridal greetings, girl's party, Nowruz, Eid-Ramadan and Eid-ul-Fitr;
- Love for the environment, protect water, air, soil, animal world, respect natural resources, do not waste them;
- Do not spit in the water, do not throw garbage, do not pollute nature, do not break trees, do not harm animals, do not kill living things;
- Visiting holy places, cemeteries, honoring them, remembering the past;
- Not to discriminate people based on nationality, race, color;
- Inseparable from history, respect for the past, etc.

These national virtues and traditions have passed through the history of the Uzbek people and become a reality. Such qualities cannot be formed by themselves, especially if a 5th grade student, who has passed from primary education to a higher grade, is educated in a specialized boarding school separated from family and social life, if we do not inculcate national qualities, we can cause great losses for the future. It is necessary to implement the above-mentioned national qualities in the student's worldview with the help of pedagogical models tested and experienced by specialized boarding school pedagogues, educator pedagogues.

According to M.Pardaeva, O.Musurmonkulova, A.Koshmanov, pedagogues demand qualities from the student of the 21st century:

There is a person who does not want to be associated with bad adjectives when talking about him. He resents the addition of words such as liar, slanderer, coward, traitor, fraudster, fool, miser, greedy. really wants to be described with good qualities like loyal, fair, intelligent, sweet, generous and hardworking. But these qualities should not only be desired, but also deserved first.[4]

This requires today's youth to:

- it is necessary to have an independent opinion - this process is taught at school in the course of subjects;
- it is necessary to know foreign languages - but it is also necessary to teach and respect one's own language perfectly;
- it is necessary to learn the laws of world development - one should not forget to develop

our country by adapting them to ourselves;

- they should spend their money on education and not luxury;
- it is necessary to dress nicely, modernly - but within the framework of etiquette, taking into account the natural climate;
- Striving for development, you should honor the history without forgetting it and be worthy of the country!

They are able to make people's lives meaningful, purposeful and happy, which, in our opinion, is very special and valuable not only from the perspective of the distant past, but also from the point of view of the present. Of course, creative and systematic use of all this in the educational process requires serious work, awareness, common sense from a person. Creative application of national and universal qualities to educational work is the key to all difficulties of education and ensuring happiness in human life. National and universal values reflect such high human qualities as humanitarianism and patriotism, culture of communication and decency: benevolence and correctness, modesty and politeness, good morals and good manners, truthfulness and honesty, kindness, benevolence, etc.

National and universal qualities are predetermined by the laws and rules of human life, according to which the education of contemporaries should be carried out, which ensures the development of society and its members. On the basis of pedagogical problems, these areas of national and universal qualities help to develop educational ideas that correspond to many pedagogical rules of our time.

Unfortunately, these valuable pedagogical ideas of the people have not yet become a subject of special study by scientific pedagogues who study the development of the pedagogical thinking of the Uzbek people.

In our opinion, the need to start a more consistent and deeper restoration of historical-cultural, national values, including pedagogically valuable traditions, customs, customs and rules of our people, has already passed.

It is known that in recent years in Uzbekistan, great works have been carried out on studying the centuries-old history of culture: education and upbringing, and a significant part of them has become the property of the world community. With the honor of the independence of our republic, lifting the veil of secrecy artificially created in the system of totalitarianism, it became possible to use those scientific discoveries not only to study the scientific truth, but also to use the material belonging to our people, which is the education of positive human moral qualities such as national pride, humanitarianism, patriotism, hard work.

In the process of new political, economic and social conditions emerging in our society, the problem of training and education of a perfect person occupies an important place. After all, the life of every person, a perfect person, has an important place in the process of renewal and development of social life. In this regard, pedagogical support for the education of a perfect person, involving the national moral qualities of folk pedagogy in this important issue.

special attention is paid to personal support.

The famous English scholar James Fraser in his "The Golden King" also considers the importance of taking into account traditions and rituals. In his opinion, if we respect the traditions and rituals of even low-cultured peoples, like searching for the truth, we will do a very smart thing.[5]

In this regard, the main focus is on improving the technology of education of national and universal qualities of the students of specialized boarding schools (preparatory, counseling, final) on the basis of professional factors (social, cultural, motivational) and integration of national and universal qualities;

identification of the most effective ethno-pedagogical ideas, methods, methods and methods in the education of the young generation expressed in the traditions, customs, traditions and teachings of folk pedagogy;

I conclude that it is necessary to determine the place of education in the qualities formed on the basis of national and universal values, its role in the development of the pedagogical thinking of the Uzbek people.

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